

Photophysics and Laser Flash Photolysis of Hydroxyquinones. Studies on Juglone and Naphthazarin[†]

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The absorption, fluorescence and phosphorescence characteristics of juglone and naphthazarin have been determined in aqueous solutions of different pH, and other solvents, like cyclohexane, carbon tetrachloride, methanol, ethylene glycol *etc.* Comparison has been made between experimental and theoretically calculated values of absorption peaks and triplet state levels. Ground and excited state pK_a values have been determined. Low quantum yields of fluorescence and phosphorescence point out to a high yield of $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ internal conversion process and possibility of photoenolisation. Preliminary results on laser flash photolysis of juglone are reported.

It has been recently suggested that semiquinones derived from quinone antitumour agents may be responsible for their antitumour action and associated cytotoxicity¹. The chemistry of hydroxyquinones has assumed significance, since these form the basic core of such quinone antitumour agents, *e.g.* adriamycin (doxorubicin) (1) which is a cytotoxic antibiotic of first line clinical importance². Juglone (5-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone) (2), itself having good antitumour activity³, and naphthazarin (5,8-dihydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone) (3) provide simple models for the internally hydrogenbonded quinonoid portion of adriamycin.

Naphthazarin also forms the basic unit of spinochromes, the pigments of echinoderms⁴. While a number of studies have been made on the photochemistry of quinones⁵, very little has been reported on the hydroxyquinones. Several reports have been published on the absorption spectral studies in methanol and chloroform⁶, absorption and pulse radiolysis of aqueous solutions of naphthazarin⁷, limited fluorescence studies of reduced products of naphthazarin in non-aqueous media⁸ *etc.* In course of our systematic photochemical studies on hydroxyquinones, we studied the absorption and luminescence characteristics of juglone and naphthazarin in a number of solvents. We report here some of our principal observations and compare our data with some theoretically calculated values. We also report here some preliminary results on the laser flash photolysis of juglone.

Experimental

Absorption spectra were recorded on a Hitachi 330 microprocessor-controlled recording spectrophotometer. Fluorescence excitation and emission spectra were recorded in a AMINCO-Bowman 4-8202B spectrofluorometer fitted with a R-136 potted photomultiplier tube and a F-42C Riken Denshi X-Y/T recorder. For concentrated solutions a front surface accessory was used. Phosphorescence spectra were recorded at 77 K in quartz tubes (2 mm i.d.), using a suitable Dewar flask and a AMINCO-Keirs phosphoroscope. A laser kinetic spectrometer (Applied Photo Physics Ltd., London) operating with a KrF excimer laser (248 nm), in conjunction with a Gould Biomation 4500 transient digitiser and a PDP 11/23 microcomputer, was used for monitoring the transient absorption and decay kinetics. A Norsk Data ND-560 computer was used for theoretical calculations and data fit. A Orion 901 digital ionalyser was used for pH measurements.

Semi-empirical self-consistent multiconfigurational calculations using π -electron PPPCI method was used for both the compounds, both for the singlet and the triplet levels. The usual version of the PPP (Pariser-Parr-Popple) method was used^{9,10}. Interactions between mono-excited configurations, formed by promotion of one electron from one of the six highest occupied π -molecular orbitals to one of the six lowest unoccupied π -molecular orbitals were considered. The systems studied were assumed to be planar and the rings were taken as regular hexagons. SCF molecular orbitals served as the basis for the CI calculations. Only resonance integrals between nearest neighbours were considered.

Fluorescence quantum yield was calculated with three different standards¹¹, (i) anthracene in cyclohexane (for $\lambda_{exc} = 260$ nm), $\phi = 0.36$; (ii) quinine bisulphate in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ (for $\lambda_{exc} = 300$,

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310 nm), $\phi=0.55$; and (iii) rhodamine-B in ethanol (for $\lambda_{exc}=490$ nm), $\phi=0.97$.

The areas under the fluorescence curves of the standard and samples were compared. Necessary corrections were made due to the small difference in optical densities of the solution and due to variation of refractive index of the solvents, by using the formula¹¹,

$$\frac{\phi_{\text{sample}}}{\phi_{\text{standard}}} = \frac{\text{Area}_{\text{sample}}}{\text{Area}_{\text{standard}}} \times \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{standard}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}}} \times \frac{n_1^2}{n_2^2} \quad (1)$$

where, n_1 and n_2 are refractive index for the solvent used for the sample and the standard, respectively. In several cases where either the fluorescence was too weak or scattering overlap was significant, quantum yield determination was not attempted.

Juglone (Sigma) and naphthazarin (synthesised sample¹²) were recrystallised from alcohol and vacuum sublimed before use. Phosphate and borate buffers, perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide were all G.R. (Sarabhai) reagents. Solvents were all spectrograde (E. Merck or Fluka). Where necessary, solutions were deoxygenated by bubbling high purity argon (Indian Oxygen) for 30 min.

Results and Discussion

The hydroxyquinones can occur in a number of states of protonation due to the ionisation of their hydroxyl groups in aqueous solutions. Thus, juglone can be either cationic (4), neutral (5) or anionic (6) in aqueous solutions, depending on pH

of the solution, while naphthazarin can be cationic (7), neutral (8), anionic (9) or dianionic (10).

Absorption studies: The absorption spectra of juglone in water, at pH values of 5 and 10.7 are shown in Fig. 1. The absorption spectra were shown to be identical throughout pH 1 to 7, showing that no ionisation took place within this range. With increasing pH (> 7), the visible peak at 420 nm gets red-shifted to 515 nm. The main uv peak at 248 nm gets slightly red-shifted to 258 nm. The spectra in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ also showed the same feature as at pH 5, showing that JH₂⁺ probably exists only in very strong acid. The wavelengths of the absorption maxima and extinction coefficient values are shown in Table 1. The large shift in λ_{max} , compared to those in 1,4-naphthoquinone⁸ is worth noting.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of juglone ($\approx 6.45 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm⁻³) in water: (—) pH 7 and (---), pH 10.5. (Inset) Variation of optical density at 560 nm for juglone as a function of pH: (O) experimental points and (—) computer best fit, with $pK_a=8.85$.

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION CHARACTERISTICS OF JUGLONE AND NAPHTHAZARIN IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS AND COMPARISON WITH SOME THEORETICALLY CALCULATED VALUES

Solvent	$\lambda_{\max}$, nm (log ϵ)	
	Juglone	Naphthazarin
Water, neutral ^a	208(4.22), 248(4.13), 310(2.98), 420(3.56)	209(4.54), 266(3.89), 340(3.03), 482(3.72), 513(3.79), 556(3.47)
Anion ^b	215(4.26), 258(3.97), 350(3.17), 515(3.61)	211(4.76), 292(3.73), 528(sh)(3.64), 579(3.81), 610(3.76)
Di-anion ^c	—	308(3.73), 575(3.94), 613(4.06)
Methanol	248(4.11), 340(sh)(3.05), 407(sh)(3.55), 422(3.56)	265(3.86), 330(3.10), 433(3.71), 511(3.73), 552(sh)(3.49)
Cyclohexane	245(3.87), 320(3.14), 406(sh)(3.58), 423(3.59)	264(4.01), 330(3.1), 486(3.87), 516(sh)(3.90), 524(3.92), 544(3.74), 5.62(3.80)
Carbon tetrachloride	323(3.07), 412(sh)(3.57), 428(3.58)	334(3.05), 489(3.78), 524(3.83), 546(3.63), 564(3.65)
PPPOI (this work)*	208(0.0941), 283(0.1448), 265(0.4956), 328(0.1003), 333(0.0580)	211(0.0537), 285(0.0930), 265(0.4850), 331(0.0055), 341(0.1701)
PPPCI ^d	233(0.08), 254(0.07), 264(0.33), 375(0.09), 418(0.10)	262(0.24), 268(0.13), 266(0.09), 402(0.0001), 417(0.16)
ONDOCI ^e	249(0.11), 262(0.001), 283(0.31), 316(0.17), 440(0.16), 445(0.06)	—

^a pH 5. ^b pH 10.7(J⁻), 9.1(NzH⁻). ^c pH ~ 13(Nz²⁻). ^d Refs, 9, 10. ^e Ref. 13. * Oscillator strength in parenthesis.

The absorbances at 420, 515 and 560 nm were measured as a function of pH over the range 5 to 11. Experimental absorbances, A_{obs} , were fitted to equation (2),

$$A_{\text{obs}} = \frac{A_1}{1 + 10^{pH - pK}} + \frac{A_2}{1 + 10^{pK - pH}} \quad (2)$$

where, A_1 and A_2 refer to absorbances attributed to the forms JH and J⁻, respectively, and pK is the pK_a value of JH. The best computer fit between the experimental and computed absorbance was obtained with $pK_a = 8.85 \pm 0.05$. The result for 560 nm is shown in the inset to Fig. 1. Other wavelengths (*viz.* 420 and 515 nm) gave the same values of pK_a . It is clear that juglone is a stronger acid than phenol or α -hydroxynaphthalene ($pK_a \sim 10$), as expected from the greater potential for delocalisation in the anionic form. Similar experiments were performed with naphthazarin. The data were identical to those reported by one of us elsewhere[†] and are shown in Table 1. The pK_a of NzH₂ and NzH⁻ were 7.85 and 10.7, respectively[†].

Absorption spectra were also recorded in cyclohexane, carbon tetrachloride, methanol and ethylene glycol. The essential features of the absorption spectra of juglone do not change much from solvent to solvent. Fig. 2 shows few such spectra. However, naphthazarin spectra show a remarkable solvent dependence (Fig. 3). Table 1 lists all the absorption maxima and extinction coefficients for both juglone and naphthazarin. It also lists the calculated maxima by different methods. There is good agreement between the experimental $\lambda_{\max}$ values and the corresponding calculated ones.

Since these compounds contain both quinonoid and benzenoid rings, it is expected that there should be a strong peri-interaction between the two rings. Thus the hydroxy groups cause a pronounced red-shift of the benzenoid absorption. Similarly, the weak $n \pi^*$ quinonoid absorptions are inter-mixed

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of juglone in some organic solvents. (—) methanol, (---) cyclohexane, (- · -) carbon tetrachloride.

with stronger $\pi \pi^*$ benzenoid absorptions. Intra-molecular hydrogen bonding also perturbs the expected absorbance values. In our calculated values (Table 1) we could not include the latter effect. It will be extremely interesting if appropriate perturbation functions for the intra-molecular H-bonding could be incorporated in the calculations. In some cases, certain calculated transitions do not show as maxima on the absorption curves because they are hidden under the envelopes of other main bands. More insight on the benzenoid and quinonoid nature of different bands could be made by our fluorescence studies.

Fluorescence studies: Quinones are well known to have extremely weak fluorescence and a high

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of naphthazarin in some organic solvents: (—) methanol, (---) cyclohexane, and (- - -) carbon tetrachloride.

inter-system crossing ($S_1 \rightarrow T_1$) rate. On the other hand, phenols and naphthols are well known for their well resolved fluorescence spectra. Juglone and naphthazarin showed characteristics of both class of compounds. Both showed weak fluorescence. While the uv excited fluorescence peaks were well resolved, the fluorescence in the visible region was broad. Fig. 4 shows juglone (JH) fluorescence, when the spectra were recorded with different excitation wavelength. While JH absorption maximum in the uv is at 248 nm, the excitation maximum was found to be ~ 310 nm. In spite of repeated purification of the sample from different batches, there was no change in the excitation or fluorescence maxima. The position of fluorescence maxima was independent of $\lambda_{\text{excitation}}$ of either 248 or 310 nm. Tlc of all the samples (silica gel) showed no sign of any impurity present. Any re-sublimable impurity, therefore, has to be $< 0.1\%$ of the quinone. The fluorescence has thus to be very strong for this impurity, with estimated quantum yield ≥ 1

(Table 2). This looked highly improbable. Another alternative¹¹ was energy transfer from one chromophore to another. In addition, CNDOCI calculations¹⁸ showed λ_{max} at 316 nm (oscillator strength = 0.17). However, this peak was not detectable in actual absorption spectra in solvents (Table 1), but could, in practice, be the basis for a more allowed fluorescence transition. In the case of naphthazarin in water and alcohol solutions, an additional strong fluorescence was observed at ~ 450 nm, when excited with 260 nm light (Fig. 5). The excitation spectrum for this 450 nm fluorescence gave a peak at ~ 400 nm in addition to 260 nm. However, the 400 nm region is only a shoulder in the absorption spectrum of naphthazarin and PPPCI calculations¹⁹ showed an extremely weak peak at 402 nm and a strong one at 416 nm. We, therefore, conclude that the 400 nm transition represent a benzenoid transition.

The quantum yields of uv-excited fluorescence from both the compounds were small (Tables 2

Fig. 4. Fluorescence spectra of juglone in different solvents : (-) ethylene glycol, (--) methanol, (...) cyclohexane, (-.-) carbon tetrachloride and (-.-.-) water (pH 5); λ_{exc} for left-hand curves, 300 nm and for right-hand curves, 400 nm.

Fig. 5. Fluorescence spectra of naphthazarin in different solvents : (-) ethylene glycol, (--) methanol, (...) cyclohexane, (-.-) carbon tetrachloride and (-.-.-) water (pH 5); λ_{exc} for left-hand curve, 300 nm ; for the middle curves, 260 nm ; and for the right-hand curves, 490 nm.

TABLE 2—FLUORESCENCE CHARACTERISTICS OF JUGLONE

Solvent	λ_{max} (fluor.) nm	E_s^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ϕ_{fl}
Water (pH 5)	334 sh ^a , 346 ^a	358.5 ^a	0.16 ^a
Methanol	336 sh ^a , 348 ^a 450 sh ^b , 435 ^b	356.4 ^a 266.1 ^b	0.085 ^a i
Ethylene glycol	336 sh ^a , 348 ^a 465 ^b , 493 ^b	356.4 ^a 257.5	0.17 i
Carbon tetrachloride	442 ^b , 463 ^b	270.9 ^b	i
Cyclohexane	336 sh ^a , 348 ^a 440 ^b , 458 ^b	356.4 ^a 279.1	0.077 i

* Determined from the shortest wavelength transition.

λ_{exc} = ^a 300, ^b 400 nm. ^b Used instead of 420 nm (exc. max.) to minimise scattering overlap. i = Indeterminate accurately due to scattering overlap.

and 3). The fluorescence induced by excitation due to absorption in the visible region had lower quantum yield in case of juglone (Table 2), but comparable in case of naphthazarin (Table 3). In completely aprotic solvents (*i.e.* CCl₄) the quantum yield was marginally increased, probably due to a decrease in S₁→S₀ internal conversion. The effect of viscosity was more significant in juglone than in naphthazarin, as shown by the use of ethylene glycol. In relatively concentrated solutions (>10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³), front surface optics were always used to avoid distortion caused by self-absorption of emitted fluorescence in the visible region when usual perpendicular optics were used. A comparison of Tables 2 and 3 also shows that the visible bands have a mixed benzenoid *gem* quinonoid character, with naphthazarin having more benzenoid character than juglone.

TABLE 3—FLUORESCENCE CHARACTERISTICS OF NAPHTHAZARIN

Solvent	λ_{max} (fluor.) nm	E_s^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ϕ_{fl}
Water (pH 5)	365 ^{a,b} , 460 ^{a,b} 585 ^c , 612 ^c	328.1 ^{a,b} 204.7 ^c	i ^{a,b} 0.022 ^c
Water (pH 9.1)	360 ^a , 420 sh ^{a,b}	332.6 ^{a,b}	—
Water (pH 12.5)	~ 400 ^{a,b}	—	—
Methanol	455 ^a , 386 ^b 585 ^c , 612 sh ^c	356.4 ^b 204.7 ^c	0.009 ^{a,c} i ^b
Ethylene glycol	362 ^{a,b} , 452 ^a 537 ^c , 618 sh ^c	330.8 ^{a,b} 204.0 ^c	0.009 ^a 0.01 ^b , 0.011 ^c
Carbon tetrachloride	331 ^b , 588 ^c , 620 ^c	361.8 ^b , 208.6 ^c	i ^b , 0.011 ^c
Cyclohexane	378 sh ^{a,b} , 450 ^a 590 ^c , 620 ^c	321.0 ^{a,b} 208.0 ^c	0.019 ^a , 0.062 ^b 0.012 ^c

* Determined from the shortest wavelength transition.

λ_{exc} = ^a 260, ^b 300, ^c 490 nm. ^b Used instead of 380 nm (exc. max.) to minimise scattering overlap. i = Indeterminate due to scattering overlap.

In aqueous solutions, we observed fluorescence from JH and NzH₂, very weak fluorescence from NzH⁻, but none from J⁻ and Nz²⁻. This shows that the molecules essentially behave like a phenol for fluorescence in aqueous solutions. Due to the absence of fluorescence from the ionic forms, only

shift in absorption could be used to calculate the excited (S₁) state pK_a values, by using equation (3).

$$pK_a = pK_a^* - \frac{Nhc}{2.303RT} (\bar{\nu}_A - \bar{\nu}_B) \quad (3)$$

where, N = Avogadro number, h = Planck constant, c = velocity of light, R = universal gas constant, T = temperature (at 298 K), and $\bar{\nu}_A, \bar{\nu}_B$ = wave number of absorption peaks.

By putting in appropriate values of 420 and 515 nm for juglone and 514 and 610 nm for naphthazarin, and using pK_a (JH) = 8.85 (this work) and pK₁ (NzH₂) = 7.35 (Ref. 7), we could calculate pK^{*} (S₁) values equal to ca -0.4 for juglone and 1.4 for naphthazarin. This explains why juglone fluorescence characteristics do not change due to change in pH from 1 to 7 and naphthazarin between pH 4 to 7. In strongly acidic solution, however, naphthazarin fluorescence was somewhat different than at pH 5.

Phosphorescence and laser flash photolysis studies: Most quinones have a near unity triplet yield⁶. Weak fluorescence from both juglone and naphthazarin indicated possibility of a strong phosphorescence. However, phosphorescence spectra determined in ethanol-methanol (4:1), ethylene glycol-water (1:1), aqueous 0.5% glucose and 3-methylpentane matrices at 77 K was found to be very weak. The quantum yield could not be accurately determined due to this weak nature of the phosphorescence. The spectral characteristics are shown in Fig. 6 and tabulated in Table 4. The low quantum yield of both fluorescence and phosphorescence probably indicate that either one or

Fig. 6 Phosphorescence spectra of juglone (λ_{exc} = 260 nm) and naphthazarin (λ_{exc} = 260 nm) at 77 K in ethanol-methanol (4:1, v/v) (—) juglone and (---) naphthazarin; and in 3-methylpentane: juglone (---) and naphthazarin (-.-).

both of S₁→S₀ internal conversion and T₁→S₀ inter-system crossing are predominant processes for such compounds. However, T₁→S₀ transition is

TABLE 4—PHOSPHORESCENCE CHARACTERISTICS AT 77 K OF JUGLONE AND NAPHTHAZARIN

Matrix used	Phosphorescence $\lambda_{\max}$ nm		ET kJ mol ⁻¹		Other bands nm	
	Juglone ^a	Naphthazarin ^b	Juglone	Naphthazarin	Juglone	Naphthazarin
Ethylene glycol-Water (1 : 1)	448	422	267.0	283.4	423, 478	408 sh, 434 sh
Ethanol-methanol (4 : 1)	428	424	279.4	282.1	402 sh, 454	399 sh, 452 sh
3-Methylpentane	415	404	288.2	296.0	—	384 sh, 418 sh
PPFCl calculation ^c (SCFOIO)	434	456	275.9	262.8	389, 476, 754	340, 476, 749

λ_{exc} = ^a 250, ^b 260 nm. ^c Refs. 9, 10.

spin-forbidden, while $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition is highly allowed, especially due to the ground state symmetry of the parent molecules. Thus, in both juglone and naphthazarin, $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ internal conversion could be the most predominant process. An alternative method was adopted to study the triplet characteristics. The transient absorption (Fig. 7) obtained in methanol solutions after 150 and 400 nanoseconds after the laser flash, in a laser kinetic spectrometer, showed two distinct peaks at 330 and 375 nm with a shoulder at ~ 360 nm. The 330 nm peak decayed faster than the 375 nm peak. Juglone semiquinone radicals have an absorption maximum¹⁴ at ~ 375 nm, but none at 330 nm. The 330 nm absorption decayed by a first order kinetics ($k = 4.4 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$) whereas

Fig. 7. Absorption spectra of the transients produced by laser flash photolysis of juglone in air-saturated and argon bubbled methanol solutions, after (●) 150 and (○) 400 ns of the laser flash.

the 375 nm peak decayed by a second order kinetics ($2k = 4.5 \times 10^7 \times \epsilon_{375} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Our preliminary assumption is that the 330 nm peak belongs to a genuine T-T absorption, while the 375 nm peak is most likely the result of absorption by juglone semiquinone produced by hydrogen abstraction from methanol by the triplet state of juglone. This hypothesis is further strengthened by the fact that in aerated solutions, the decay of 330 nm peak is faster and that of 375 nm peak slower than in

de-oxygenated solutions. In aerated solutions, juglone semiquinone undergoes an equilibrium reaction with oxygen¹⁴,

The laser flash photolysis studies thus show that the triplet population must be significant and therefore, $T_1 \rightarrow S_0$ inter-system-crossing must be responsible for the weak phosphorescence observed. Alternatively, either the phosphorescence life-time could be very short ($ca \leq \text{microsecond}$) to elude determination by a conventional phosphoroscope, or, $T_1 \rightarrow S_0$ deactivation could be caused due to the photoionisation¹⁵ in the excited state as follows,

Further support for our hypothesis could be obtained from the observations that excited quinizarin (1,4-dihydroxy-9,10-anthraquinone) was capable of abstracting hydrogen from different solvents¹⁶ and that excited 1-hydroxy-9,10-anthraquinone undergoes fast radiationless decay in 3-methylpentane, but shows weak phosphorescence in diethyl ether-ethanol due to breaking of intra-molecular hydrogen bonds by the solvent¹⁷. We hope to resolve the exact nature of the transitions by our comprehensive laser flash photolysis studies with the hydroxyquinones¹⁸.

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